

SPECIFICITY OF THE IMAGE OF THE MAIN CHARACTER IN THE STORY "HAPPINESS" BY KATHERINE MANSFIELD

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Abstract: The short story "Happiness" ("Bliss", 1918) by Katherine Mansfield (1918), a famous master of modernist English short fiction, is a work centered on the image of a married woman, associated with the motifs of female identity, self-knowledge, self-representation, etc. This article highlights specificity of the image of the main character in the story "Happiness" of Katherine Mansfield.

Keywords: writer, writer's style, prose, comparative analysis, story.

After the First World War, in the era of a radical revision of British values, the heroine, as I.A. Shishkova, in her article on the work of Charlotta Mary Yonge (1823-1901), due to long-standing family traditions, "was proud of her fate and did not consider the postulates of Victorian morality as an obstacle to the realization of her goals" (Shishkova, 2017). Interestingly, despite the difference in spelling, the names of the Victorian children's writer and the main character of the story, K. Mansfield (Young and Yonge), are pronounced the same.

From the very beginning of the story, Bertha Young, whose speaking last name emphasizes her youth (eng. "young" - young), is characterized through a chain of verbs of movement (to run instead of walk, to take dancing steps, to throw something in the air). Bertha is thirty years old, she has a child, but she still sometimes feels like running, dancing, throwing something in the air, laughing for no reason. Bertha's soul is often overwhelmed with a feeling of bliss and happiness. It is no coincidence that the name of the heroine Bertha, through alliteration, is associated with the noun bliss, which the author puts in the title of the story. This phonetic echo hints that the feeling of happiness is as if "built into" Bertha's inner essence. The indicated alliteration clearly echoes the word body, which sounds in a fragment of the heroine's internal monologue, the body, whose life is limited by civilizational boundaries, is compared with a violin in a case: "Why be given a body if you have to keep it shut up in a case like a rare fiddle". The chain of alliteratively connected nouns Bertha, bliss, body, baby, which is built up, indicates that Bertha feels this experience of bliss from her bodily presence in the world. It is no coincidence that in the text of the story the heroine is introduced precisely as a bodily being; her movements are swift, her body exudes warmth and cannot bear the constraining tightness of clothing.

Running into the gloomy dining room, Berta takes off her coat: "It was dusky in the dining-room and quite chilly. But all the same Bertha threw off her coat; she could not bear the tight clasp of it another ment" (Mansfield, 2016). As a young mother, Bertha feels true happiness from her bodily contact CO with her child, whose image, through the aforementioned phonetic repetition of the sound b, is built into the lexical series Bertha, bliss, body.

In this context, the question of Berta, who asks the maid, has brought fruit, is also symbolic. The joyful feeling of the radiant Bertha with her premonition of some unrealizable happiness, combined with the picturesque images of fruits, refers the reader to the image of Eve, who has not yet tasted the bitterness of knowledge and is innocent in her natural corporality. Let's pay attention to how picturesquely and in detail the author depicts fruits. In front of the quivering Bertha, whose lips tremble and her eyes sparkle, is a real fruity splendor - tangerines and apples with pink spots, silky yellow pears, bunches of white and purple grapes, which she picks up to match the color of the carpet. The exquisite materiality of this still life echoes the description of the bodily shell of Bertha herself. A charming hostess who buys grapes by virtue of an aesthetic impulse, and her purchases, as it were, merge into one visual image.

Both in the description of Bertha herself and in this literary still life, a modernist attitude to the aestheticization of the familiar and everyday is found. Moreover, this attitude is shared both by the narrator himself, on whose behalf the story is being told, and by the heroine, admiring the fruits and their compatibility with the color of the interior. In this context, the appearance of the key to this story poetic comparison of the roini with a pear tree blooming in her garden is organic. Bertha compares its flowering with her prosperous and prosperous life: "... wide open blossoms as a symbol of her own life", and its beauty: "... a tall, slender pear tree in fullest, richest bloom" - with her body. Just as a flowering tree is completely covered with blossoming buds, Bertha is full of happiness that she cannot contain: "... suddenly by a feeling of bliss - absolute bliss."

Even her outfit (white dress, green stockings, shoes and beads), which she carefully selects for the arrival of guests, resembles the colors of a pear tree. The use of epithets with a positive connotation slender, perfect, superlative adjectives fullest, richest bloom in the description of the tree conveys Berta's innate state, her idealistic, largely childish picture of the world. The metaphorical comparison of a tree with a ship, which is facilitated by the use of the word becalmed against the background of a calm sky-sea against the jade-

green sky, creates an image of a ship that has found its peace in the bay of a joyful family life.

It should be noted that in the context of modernist artistry, the image of a tree is often interpreted precisely in the light of its ancient archaism. So, for example, in the modernist novel *Orlando* by W. Wolfe, the tree appears as a comprehensive symbol of life. As N.V. Morzhenkov, "the oak tree is <...> cultural sythesis, mythological universal tree unifying three worlds (underworld - middle world - heaven), and three times (past-present-future)" (Morzhenkova, 2004). It is obvious that the aesthetic Bertha looks at the pear tree precisely through such a cultural prism.

Admiring the tree, the heroine notices two cats sneaking around the garden. The verbs with the semantics of the slow movement "drag, creep, trail" (so contrasting compared to the impetuous movements of Bertha herself) and the color epithets "black, gray", contrasting with the festive whiteness of the pear flowers, give this scene an ominous character. It seems that the immaculate garden, which is metaphorically compared to Bertha's family life, is in danger. Indeed, the image of cats, traditionally associated with motives of sexual lust and betrayal, anticipates the unexpected denouement of the story.

The image of the heroine is largely created through luminous metaphor. Happiness glows inside Berta, as if she swallowed a piece of the sun (a bright piece of that late afternoon sun sending out a little shower of sparks into every particle) (Mansfield, 2016).

She tries to restrain her emotions, and putting things in order in the living room, presses a pillow to her chest, but even that is unable to calm the happiness burning inside her (the fire in her bosom), which is now compared by means of a metaphor no longer with sunlight, but with fire. Strengthening the luminous metaphors allows us to trace the causeless growth of Bertha's feelings from harmless sunlight to the fire that devours her from the inside.

It is significant that if at the beginning of the story Bertha appears as a charming creature with a little oddity, then as all this metaphor of happiness grows, the reader begins to feel the obvious excess and exaltation of both the narrative itself and the behavior of the heroine. Just as a short story seems unable to organically contain all this romantically elevated vocabulary, so the life of the heroine, her very status as a bourgeois lady, turn out to be too common for such intense emotions, which by the middle of the story begin to be perceived as manifestations of feigned eccentricity and exaggerated sensitivity. Her spiritual "burning" is unmotivated. Thus, the motif of falsehood and

pretense is actualized in the story precisely at the level of style. In the course of reading the story, it begins to seem “suspicious”, first of all, precisely too active stylistic expressiveness, the appearance of which is not motivated by either the plot or the genre.

Obviously, in this story, the modernist practice of aestheticization and mythologization of the entire image becomes the object of parody. For example, speaking about the specifics of the modernist autobiography, N.V. Morzhenkova notes that “in the context of modernist autobiographical writing, the question of the interaction of artistic and documentary plans, the distinction between authentic and fictitious autobiography becomes more complicated” (Morzhenkova, 2016). So Berta in the story under consideration creates her fictitious image of a young, refined aesthetic, despite her position as a middle-aged woman belonging to the bourgeoisie.

The sense of falsehood is heightened in the scene describing the reception at Mrs. Young's house, which is attended by wealthy guests with a claim to intelligence and refined taste. The introduction of a new character, Miss Pearl Fulton, who attracted Bertha with her aloof beauty and mystery, introduces a cold motif into the story, contrasting with the “hot” imagery associated with the heroine. When describing Pearl Fulton, the author uses epithets related to cold colors (all in silver, with a silver fillet binding her pale blonde hair). The very name Pearl (eng. pear]! - a pearl) acts as a color metaphor, emphasizing the coldness and superhumanity of the heroine. Even Miss Fulton's fingers are likened to moonbeams and described with the epithet moonbeam.

At the lexical level, the antithesis of heat and cold appears in the text, which, at the heroic level, correlates with the opposition of the two heroines. Sunny Berta is beckoned by moon Pearl. She admires it as a piece of art. An image of a garden and a tree pops up in Bertha's memory, and for a moment the tree, bathed in the silver light of the moon, is metaphorically identified in Bertha's mind with Miss Fulton: “It would be silver now, silver as Miss Fulton” (Mansfield, 2016). The moon, which is mythologically associated with lies and adultery, is a harbinger of evil.

In the episode in which Bertha shows Miss Fulton the garden, the tree is compared to a burning candle (like the flame of a candle), the flame of which flutters, visually increases, tries to reach the moon itself. Thanks to the verbs with the semantics of “action” (Stretch up, point, grow, touch), the motif of animation is introduced, the tree is presented as a living being. The image of the garden and the tree reappears at the end of the story, when Bertha becomes an

accidental witness to the exchange of love tenderness between her husband and Miss Fulton. She looks at the garden and asks a rhetorical question: "Oh, what is going to happen now?" Berta understands that her family life has collapsed, her simulated happiness has disappeared. However, the tree with which she compared herself and her well-being continues to bloom, as before.

Unexpectedly (both for the heroine herself and for the reader), the denouement of the story about spiritual premonitions and aesthetic "revelations" ends in a trivial adultery, which is quite typical for the reception of an "unreliable narrator". Moreover, if purely formally the narration is conducted from an external point of view from a third person, then at the level of style we feel the "gluing" of the point of view of the heroine herself and the narrator. The author's word is "colored" with exalted intonations of the character's word.

However, the emasculation of this simulated sensitivity and sophistication is fully revealed precisely at the very end of the story, when the comic image of the main character is revealed. According to V.I. Tyupy, the comic image of the character sets "a comic gap between the inner and outer sides of the "I-in-the-world", between the face and the mask" (Tyupy, 1997). Under the empty role-playing mask of a sophisticated aesthetic, there is a bewildered deceived woman, under the mystery of Miss Fulton - a secret affair with a married man. In this world of imaginary and pretense, only the natural beauty of a pear blossom remains unchanged and equal to itself.

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